

Tentative Outline
Special Issue for Current Organic Chemistry
Guest Editor(s): Morteza Shiri

TITLE: Synthesis of heterocycles via cascade reactions

Aims & Scope:

Heterocycles are of interest molecules in the aspects of synthesis, biological activity evaluations and physical properties etc. In past two decade tandem, domino or cascade reactions made an advanced in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds as well as other molecules. Because of the importance of heterocycles in the field of medicinal chemistry as well as other chemical industry, seems to be interesting the synthesis of such compounds. Tandem process as powerful tool in the hands of synthetic chemists made them able to assemble complex molecules. There are many separate articles in the journals which address the title of "Synthesis of heterocycles via cascade reactions" but arranging one or more special issues by this framework in *Current Organic Chemistry* would be a welcome resource for researcher in the field.

Keywords:

Cascade reactions, Tandem reactions, Domino reactions, Heterocyclic compounds, Synthesis, Natural products, Transition metals, Organocatalysts

Subtopics:

- Recent Advances in the assembling of heterocyclic compounds by cascade reactions
- Isocyanide based aza-heterocyclic synthesis by cascade reaction
- Cascade reactions catalysed by transition metals in the synthesis of heterocycles
- Organocatalytic cascade reaction in the synthesis of heterocycles
- Synthesis of azaheterocycles
- Designing of new pathways in the synthesis of heterocycles
- Construction of polyheterocycles
- Synthesis of new diversity of heterocycles
- Cascade reaction in the synthesis of heterocyclic natural products
- Cascade reactions in chemical industry
- Asymmetric domino reactions
- Functionalization of heterocycles via tandem reactions
- Domino reactions under green solvents

Approximate Schedule:

- Manuscript submission deadline: Feb 2016
- Peer Review Due: Apr 2016
- Revision Due: May 2016
- Notification of acceptance by the Guest Editor: Jun 2016
- Final manuscript due: Jul 2016